

On the analytic solution of a no-interaction research system model

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1 Model

1.1 Infinitesimal scholars with a distribution

Assume that the distribution of scholars' quality q_i follow a beta distribution

$$f(q_i; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} q_i^{\alpha-1} (1 - q_i)^{\beta-1}, \quad (1)$$

where $0 \leq q_i \leq 1$. The beta distribution allow us to have a flexible distribution while being analytically tractable (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Probability distribution function of beta distribution

The expected payoff of scholar i applying for funding is

$$a(s_i)y(q_i, s_i) - c(q_i, s_i). \quad (2)$$

where $a(s_i)$ represents the success probability, $y(q_i, s_i)$ represents the payoff, $c(q_i, s_i)$ represents the cost, q_i represents the quality of scholar i , s_i represents the proposal strength picked by the scholar.

To simplify the problem, assume

$$a(s_i) = a_0 s_i^k, \quad (3)$$

$$y(q_i, s_i) = y_0 q_i, \quad (4)$$

$$c(q_i, s_i) = c_0 s_i^{l_s} q_i^{l_q}, \quad (5)$$

The overall success probability p depends on all the individual probability $a(s_i)$. Assume that scholar i picks the optimal strength s_i ,

$$s_i = \left(\frac{c_0 l_s q_i^{l_q - 1}}{a_0 y_0 k} \right)^{\frac{1}{k - l_s}}. \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} p &= \int f(q_i; \alpha, \beta) a(s_i) dq_i, \\ &= \int_0^1 \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} q_i^{\alpha - 1} (1 - q_i)^{\beta - 1} \left(\frac{c_0 l_s q_i^{l_q - 1}}{a_0 y_0 k} \right)^{\frac{k}{k - l_s}} a_0 dq_i, \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \left(\frac{c_0 l_s}{a_0 y_0 k} \right)^{\frac{k}{k - l_s}} a_0 \int_0^1 q_i^{\alpha + \frac{k(l_q - 1)}{k - l_s} - 1} (1 - q_i)^{\beta - 1} dq_i, \\ &= a_0 \left(\frac{c_0 l_s}{a_0 y_0 k} \right)^{\frac{k}{k - l_s}} \left(\frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta)\Gamma(\alpha + \frac{k(l_q - 1)}{k - l_s})}{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + \frac{k(l_q - 1)}{k - l_s})\Gamma(\alpha)} \right). \end{aligned}$$

We can compute the expected payoff of the whole population by first computing the expected gain and the expected cost.

The expected gain:

$$\begin{aligned} &\int y(q_i, s_i) f(q_i; \alpha, \beta) a(s_i) dq_i, \\ &= \int_0^1 y_0 q_i \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} q_i^{\alpha - 1} (1 - q_i)^{\beta - 1} \left(\frac{c_0 l_s q_i^{l_q - 1}}{a_0 y_0 k} \right)^{\frac{k}{k - l_s}} a_0 dq_i, \\ &= a_0 y_0 \left(\frac{c_0 l_s}{a_0 y_0 k} \right)^{\frac{k}{k - l_s}} \left(\frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta)\Gamma(\alpha + \frac{k(l_q - 1)}{k - l_s} + 1)}{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + \frac{k(l_q - 1)}{k - l_s} + 1)\Gamma(\alpha)} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, the expected cost:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int c(q_i, s_i) f(q_i; \alpha, \beta) dq_i, \\
&= \int_0^1 c_0 \left(\frac{c_0 l_s q_i^{l_q-1}}{a_0 y_0 k} \right)^{\frac{l_s}{k-l_s}} q_i^{l_q} \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} q_i^{\alpha-1} (1 - q_i)^{\beta-1} dq_i, \\
&= c_0 \left(\frac{c_0 l_s}{a_0 y_0 k} \right)^{\frac{l_s}{k-l_s}} \left(\frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta) \Gamma(\alpha + \frac{l_s(l_q-1)}{k-l_s} + l_q)}{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + \frac{l_s(l_q-1)}{k-l_s} + l_q) \Gamma(\alpha)} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

The expected payoff is equal to the expected gain subtracting the expected cost

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{\text{infinitesimal}} = & a_0 y_0 \left(\frac{c_0 l_s}{a_0 y_0 k} \right)^{\frac{k}{k-l_s}} \left(\frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta) \Gamma(\alpha + \frac{k(l_q-1)}{k-l_s} + 1)}{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + \frac{k(l_q-1)}{k-l_s} + 1) \Gamma(\alpha)} \right) \\
& - c_0 \left(\frac{c_0 l_s}{a_0 y_0 k} \right)^{\frac{l_s}{k-l_s}} \left(\frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta) \Gamma(\alpha + \frac{l_s(l_q-1)}{k-l_s} + l_q)}{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + \frac{l_s(l_q-1)}{k-l_s} + l_q) \Gamma(\alpha)} \right). \tag{7}
\end{aligned}$$

Define the efficiency as the ratio of the expected payoff and the payoff from the perfect allocation configuration. In this model, the perfect allocation configuration means that given p portion of the population is funded, all the funding goes into the best p portion of the distribution with a 100% of success probability, where others simply do not apply.

The expected gain in the perfect allocation configuration

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int y(q_i, s_i) f(q_i; \alpha, \beta) dq_i, \\
&= \int_{F^{-1}(1-p; \alpha, \beta)}^1 y_0 q_i \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} q_i^{\alpha-1} (1 - q_i)^{\beta-1} dq_i, \\
&= y_0 \frac{\alpha}{\alpha + \beta} \int_{F^{-1}(1-p; \alpha, \beta)}^1 \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + 1)}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)\Gamma(\beta)} q_i^\alpha (1 - q_i)^{\beta-1} dq_i, \\
&= y_0 \frac{\alpha}{\alpha + \beta} (1 - F(F^{-1}(1 - p; \alpha, \beta)); \alpha + 1, \beta),
\end{aligned}$$

where $F(x; \alpha, \beta)$ is the incomplete beta function and $F^{-1}(x; \alpha, \beta)$ is the inverse incomplete beta function.

The expected cost in the perfect allocation configuration

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int c(q_i, s_i) f(q_i; \alpha, \beta) dq_i, \\
&= \int_{F^{-1}(1-p; \alpha, \beta)}^1 c_0 \left(\frac{c_0 l_s q_i^{l_q-1}}{a_0 y_0 k} \right)^{\frac{l_s}{k-l_s}} q_i^{l_q} \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} q_i^{\alpha-1} (1 - q_i)^{\beta-1} dq_i, \\
&= c_0 \left(\frac{c_0 l_s}{a_0 y_0 k} \right)^{\frac{l_s}{k-l_s}} \left(\frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta) \Gamma(\alpha + \frac{l_s(l_q-1)}{k-l_s} + l_q)}{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + \frac{l_s(l_q-1)}{k-l_s} + l_q) \Gamma(\alpha)} \right) \\
&\quad \times (1 - F(F^{-1}(1 - p; \alpha, \beta)); \alpha + \frac{l_s(l_q - 1)}{k - l_s} + l_q, \beta)).
\end{aligned}$$

Subtracting the cost from the gain to get the expected payoff in the perfect allocation configuration

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{\text{perfect infinitesimal}} &= y_0 \frac{\alpha}{\alpha + \beta} (1 - F(F^{-1}(1 - p; \alpha, \beta)); \alpha + 1, \beta) \\
&\quad - c_0 \left(\frac{c_0 l_s}{a_0 y_0 k} \right)^{\frac{l_s}{k-l_s}} \left(\frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta) \Gamma(\alpha + \frac{l_s(l_q-1)}{k-l_s} + l_q)}{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + \frac{l_s(l_q-1)}{k-l_s} + l_q) \Gamma(\alpha)} \right) \quad (8) \\
&\quad \times (1 - F(F^{-1}(1 - p; \alpha, \beta)); \alpha + \frac{l_s(l_q - 1)}{k - l_s} + l_q, \beta).
\end{aligned}$$

The efficiency is defined as

$$\epsilon_{\text{infinitesimal}} = \frac{E_{\text{infinitesimal}}}{E_{\text{perfect infinitesimal}}}. \quad (9)$$

2 Results

2.1 Efficiency in the infinitesimal scholars model

There are 7 free variables in the model, since a_0 and y_0 both have a meaning of the amount of funding, we fix $a_0 = 0.2$. Since the cost of preparing an application should be proportional to the proposal strength, we take $c_0 = 1$ and $l_s = 2$. We also fix $l_q = -1$ and $k = 1$ to make the cost of preparing a proposal can be inversely proportional to scholar's quality, and the chance of success to be proportional to the proposal strength. y_0 is varied from 1 to 50 to show the effect of increasing the amount of funding.

Firstly, we should ensure that the overall portion of funded application make sense in our chosen range of parameters. Fig. 2 shows that the funded

Figure 2: Overall funded portion as a function of the amount of funding y_0

portion increases with the amount of funding y_0 , while it is below 1, so our parameter settings are reasonable.

Fig. 3 demonstrate how the efficiency $\epsilon_{\text{infinitesimal}}$ (see Eq. 9 changes with the amount of funding y_0 . In general, the efficiency increases with y_0 . We propose that this is due to the scholar with higher quality benefit more from the increase of funding, so the higher the amount of funding, the more "weight" from high quality scholars, thus approaching the perfect allocation configuration.

Figure 3: Efficiency in the infinitesimal scholar model versus the amount of funding y_0